

TRANSFORMING PAKISTAN'S CRIMINAL JUSTICE SYSTEM: CONFRONTING COLONIAL LEGACIES AND CONTEMPORARY CHALLENGES

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Abstract

The criminal justice system in Pakistan continues to function under the enduring shadow of colonial era, structures, policies, and institutional mindsets inherited from British rule. Despite over more than seven decades of independence, reforms have largely remained superficial, failing to deliver equitable, timely, and transparent justice to citizens. This research aims to critically examine the colonial foundations of Pakistan's criminal justice system and the extent to which they have influenced present day practices, particularly in policing, trial procedures, and punishment mechanisms.

The central research objective is to explore how both historical legacies and contemporary challenges interact to hinder meaningful reforms, and to identify viable pathways for transformation. Employing a qualitative research design, the study uses doctrinal legal analysis and comparative institutional review, supplemented by semi-structured interviews with legal professionals, police officials, and human rights activists. Primary and secondary data sources, including statutory laws, policy papers and case laws etc., have been thoroughly examined to uncover patterns of continuity and change.

The findings reveal that many institutional inefficiencies such as outdated criminal procedure codes, discretionary policing practices, and punitive approaches to justice are deeply rooted in colonial control mechanisms designed to suppress rather than serve. Furthermore, modern realities like political interference, judicial delays, lack of forensic capacity, and socio-economic disparities exacerbate the crisis. Efforts at reform have often stumbled due to structural inertia, bureaucratic resistance, and inadequate stakeholder coordination.

The study concludes that holistic reforms must begin with the decolonization of legal consciousness and institutional ethos. Transforming police accountability, modernizing trial procedures, ensuring access to legal aid, and promoting restorative justice approaches are critical. The research underscores the need for a multi-pronged strategy involving legislative overhaul, institutional restructuring, public engagement, and capacity building. These reforms are not only essential for upholding the rule of law but also for restoring public trust in the justice system.

The paper provides actionable insights for policymakers, legal practitioners, and scholars, advocating for a justice system that aligns with constitutional values, human rights standards, and the needs of a democratic society.

INTRODUCTION

The criminal justice system in Pakistan, more than seventy-five years after independence, continues to reflect the enduring legacies of colonial governance. The current legal system in Pakistan was brought about by British colonization and is extremely difficult for locals to understand. Several problems and difficulties have tainted it for a long time, despite significant legislative and judicial reforms, the system has failed to provide victims of crimes with prompt and equitable justice, and severe inadequacies continue to damage Pakistani citizens' lives. (Sufi, Soomro, & Soomro, 2023) Although the country emerged as a sovereign nation in 1947, the legal and institutional structure that regulate its criminal justice mechanisms remain substantially inherited from British colonial rule. These inherited arrangements were designed primarily for control and subjugation, not justice or fairness. Consequently, the criminal justice apparatus ranging from the police to the courts and penal institutions has failed to evolve meaningfully in ways that reflect the democratic and constitutional ideals of a modern republic.

Over time, some laws lose their relevance but remain part of legal codes, either due to oversight or bureaucratic inertia. While some outdated laws are simply amusing, others can cause serious legal issues, impacting individuals, businesses, and entire communities. (Fleming, 2025) The persistence of outdated laws, archaic procedures, and authoritarian policing methods has led to a justice system that is often slow, inaccessible, and disproportionately punitive, particularly for marginalized communities. This research paper sets out to explore the deeply entrenched colonial foundations of Pakistan's criminal justice system, interrogating the ways in which these legacies continue to shape present-day practices. The study focuses specifically on policing, prosecution, judicial trial procedures, and punishment mechanisms to uncover the extent of continuity between colonial-era practices and contemporary challenges. It also analyzes how these

historical legacies interact with modern-day socio-political realities such as political interference, lack of resources, bureaucratic inefficiencies, and socioeconomic disparities to create a system resistant to reform. Despite periodic efforts at reform, many initiatives have failed to address the systemic issues that obstruct the delivery of fair, timely, and transparent justice. Though seemingly irrelevant, outdated laws can still impact daily life in surprising ways. Individuals may find themselves inadvertently breaking laws that no longer make sense in modern contexts. Businesses, property owners, and even social behaviors can be constrained by archaic legal system. These laws can also be wielded selectively, leading to inconsistent enforcement and legal ambiguity. (Fleming, 2025)

The necessity of reform in Pakistan's criminal justice system is widely acknowledged by academics, practitioners, and policymakers. However, the discourse often overlooks the foundational influence of colonial rule on the justice system's current inefficiencies. This oversight has led to piecemeal and reactive approaches, rather than comprehensive, forward-looking reforms. For instance, the Criminal Procedure Code (CrPC) of 1898 remains largely intact, while police practices still reflect a colonial mentality of suspicion, coercion, and control. Courts are overburdened, justice delivery is delayed, and prisons are overcrowded all symptoms of a deeper structural malaise rooted in a legal consciousness that privileges order over justice. Justice Amjad Ali Sahito of the Sind High Court was of the view that the amendments were necessary to change the old laws, including criminal procedure code (CrPC), in order to bring improvements to the criminal justice system, while Justice Sahito stated that in order to discourage frivolous and false litigation, there must be some deterrence and penalty/fines must be imposed upon the complainants for lodging fake First Information Reports (FIRs). Whereas Justice Adnan-ul-Karim Memon of the Sind High Court also recommended changes in the laws and said that such

changes would empower the prosecutor in respect of the scrutiny of the charge-sheets/investigation reports. (Tanoli, 2024)

This research paper adopts a qualitative methodology to explore the historical and structural barriers to reform. Using doctrinal legal analysis and comparative institutional review, supplemented by semi-structured interviews with legal professionals, police officials, and human rights advocates, the study offers a multi-dimensional view of the criminal justice system's enduring failures. Both primary and secondary sources such as statutory laws, case laws, policy reports, and expert testimonies have been analyzed to trace patterns of continuity and identify emerging avenues for change. The interviews provide invaluable insight into how practitioners within the system perceive its shortcomings and what reforms they believe are necessary to move toward a more equitable and rights-based legal system.

The findings of this research reveal that institutional inefficiencies are not merely the result of poor management or corruption, but are deeply embedded in the original colonial design of the system. The colonial administration established legal institutions to maintain state power and suppress dissent, rather than to ensure justice for the populace. This foundational purpose continues to resonate in the form of unchecked police discretion, prosecutorial dominance, and adversarial trial systems that prioritize conviction over truth. Furthermore, contemporary challenges such as public awareness, political manipulation of legal institutions, lack of forensic capacity, insufficient legal aid, and inadequate training of law enforcement and judiciary compound these inherited flaws.

This study argues that meaningful reform must begin with the decolonization of the legal mindset and institutional culture. Reforming the criminal justice system requires more than amending a few outdated laws or introducing new policies. It demands a fundamental rethinking of how justice is conceptualized, administered, and experienced. Priority areas include police accountability and independence, proper police training, modernization of trial procedures through technology to enhance the trial capacity for accuracy & speedy justice by

acquittal or conviction, witness protection for authentic testimony, expansion of legal aid networks to ensure access to justice, and the promotion of restorative justice practices over punitive incarceration. These reforms must be backed by a coherent strategy involving legislative overhaul, institutional restructuring, community engagement, and investment in capacity-building across all tiers of the justice system.

Ultimately, transforming Pakistan's criminal justice system is essential not only for upholding the rule of law but also for fostering public trust, social cohesion, and democratic governance. A justice system that perpetuates colonial-era injustices cannot serve the needs of a modern, pluralistic society. The insights offered by this research aim to contribute to an informed discourse on reform, providing concrete recommendations for policymakers, legal professionals, and scholars committed to building a system that aligns with constitutional values, international human rights standards, and the aspirations of the Pakistani people.

BRIEF HISTORICAL BACKGROUND:

The evolution of the criminal justice system in Pakistan is deeply rooted in its colonial past and has undergone gradual, yet often inadequate, reforms over time. During the British colonial rule (1858-1947), the system was primarily designed to maintain control over the local population rather than ensure justice. Key legislations such as the Indian Penal Code (1860), the Criminal Procedure Code (1898), and the Police Act (1861) established a centralized, rigid, and state-centric justice system. Following independence in 1947, Pakistan inherited this legal infrastructure with minimal alterations; the Pakistan Penal Code (PPC) was adapted from the Indian Penal Code (IPC) 1860, and Criminal Procedure Code 1898 (CrPC) continued to govern criminal procedures. The British-influenced adversarial judicial system remained intact, and courts continued to rely on colonial precedents. A major shift occurred during General Zia-ul-Haq's regime (1977-1988), which marked the Islamization of criminal law through the introduction of the Hudood Ordinances (1979) and Qisas and Diyat laws, adding religious dimensions to an already complex legal structure. In the modern democratic

era (1988-present), constitutional protections such as the right to a fair trial (Article 10A) and safeguards against self-incrimination and double jeopardy (Article 13) were reinforced, and the judiciary gradually asserted its independence, particularly post-2000s. Efforts toward reform at provincial level included the Khyber Pakhtunkhwa Police Order 2002, Police Act 2017 and Police amendment Act 2024 whereas at federal level the National Judicial Policy 2009, the establishment of specialized courts, and the integration of technology such as E-Courts and video link hearings.

The colonial legacy endures through outdated statutes like the CrPC 1898 and PPC 1860, and police behavior remains coercive and politically influenced. Judicial delays, low conviction rates, and poor victim protection further erode public trust. In recent years, attention has turned to human rights issues, gender-based violence, and alternative dispute resolution mechanisms, with laws like the Zainab Alert Act 2020 addressing pressing social concerns. Despite these advances, sustainable reform demands political will, institutional integrity, and a shift from state-centric to victim-centric justice.

LITERATURE REVIEW:

Sufi, Soomro I.A, and Soomro M.M, (2023) critically examine the colonial origins and enduring deficiencies of Pakistan's criminal justice system. Despite various legislative and judicial reforms, the system remains inaccessible and ineffective for the average citizen, failing to deliver timely and equitable justice. The study highlights persistent issues such as maladministration, corruption, lack of resources, and weak coordination between investigative and prosecutorial bodies, which often allow offenders to escape accountability. The authors stress the urgent need for comprehensive reforms in criminal laws including the Code of Criminal Procedure 1898 (CrPC), Pakistan Penal Code 1860 (PPC), and Qanoon-e-Shahadat as well as systemic administrative changes to restore public trust and ensure equal justice for all.

Fleming (2025) explores how outdated laws, despite being misaligned with modern societal values, continue to shape legal systems due to legislative inertia, bureaucratic complexity, and historical reverence. These obsolete laws persist in various

forms from archaic morality statutes and property laws to outdated licensing and business regulations often causing confusion, reinforcing outdated norms, or allowing selective enforcement. Fleming highlights how such laws can still influence individual behavior, hinder economic opportunities, and perpetuate systemic inequality through legal loopholes and conflicting statutes. Particularly in criminal justice, unrepealed laws may result in disproportionate sentencing, wrongful convictions, and inconsistencies in legal proceedings. The article underscores the urgent need for systemic reform, emphasizing the role of legislative action, judicial reinterpretation, and public advocacy in repealing or updating such laws to ensure fairness, consistency, and societal relevance within the legal framework.

Experts and judicial authorities at the 19th Pakistan Prosecution Forum emphasized the urgent need to reform Pakistan's colonial-era Criminal Procedure Code (CrPC) to modernize and improve the criminal justice system. Key concerns included the lack of coordination between police and prosecutors, defective investigations, and reliance on outdated investigative practices. High Court judges, including Justice Amjad Ali Sahito and Justice Adnan-ul-Karim Memon, advocated for integrating forensic tools, ensuring physical presence of accused in court, penalizing frivolous litigation, and empowering prosecutors in charge-sheet scrutiny. Prosecutor Generals from Sindh, Punjab, and Balochistan highlighted challenges such as limited budgets, lack of witness protection, and outdated procedures, especially police under section 173 CrPC required to file charge-sheet within a period of fourteen days whereas police have a right to submit a charge-sheet even after the submission of the final report and to conduct investigation as long as it was not based on mala fides. (2002 PCr. LJ 310). The forum concluded that meaningful legal and judicial reforms were essential to address structural inefficiencies and outdated practices in Pakistan's justice system. (Tanoli, 2024)

The criminal justice system in Pakistan remains deeply rooted in colonial-era legal frameworks and institutional cultures that were originally designed to serve the administrative and coercive needs of the British Empire rather than principles of justice, equity, or public welfare. Scholarly literature has

widely documented how British colonial authorities instituted laws and bureaucratic structures with the primary objective of controlling dissent and maintaining imperial dominance, not ensuring access to justice (Newburn, 2017; Jalal, 1995). Consequently, the continuity of these institutions post-independence has created systemic inertia that resists transformative reform, resulting in a criminal justice apparatus characterized by inefficiency, arbitrariness, and authoritarianism.

The study of Colonial Legacies of British a narrative analysis of police service of Pakistan by Fida Muhammad Khan, Aftab Alam & Manzoor Ali Vesperio critically examines how colonial legacies continue to shape the structure, function, and culture of the Police Service of Pakistan (PSP). Drawing upon institutional theory and post-colonial legal system, it traces the roots of Pakistan's police system to the Royal Irish Constabulary (RIC) model, which was implemented in British India primarily to maintain colonial control and suppress dissent. The Police Act of 1861 laid the legal and structural foundation of the PSP, designed to serve imperial interests through coercion, fear, and unaccountable authority. (Khan, Alam, & Vesperio, 2023)

Despite Pakistan's independence in 1947, the PSP has largely retained its colonial character. Multiple reform attempts including those by Zulfikar Ali Bhutto and General Musharraf failed to bring substantive change due to bureaucratic resistance, political interference, and institutional inertia. The police are still perceived as an extractive institution characterized by corruption, abuse of power, inefficiency, and mistrust by the public.

The study highlights how reforms often ignore the behavioral and cultural continuities from colonial times. Scholars such as Suddle (2003), Petzschmann (2010), and Malik & Qureshi (2021) emphasize the need for decentralization, accountability, and public trust. However, elite control and a centralized policing model have obstructed progress. The institutional culture of superiority, detachment from citizens, and resistance to accountability is deeply embedded and shaped by its colonial origins.

The theoretical framework draws on Institutional Theory (North, 1989; Acemoglu et al., 2001) and post-colonial critiques (Alvi, 1972), arguing that formal institutions (laws, acts) have changed

marginally, but informal institutions (policing culture, officer attitudes) have persisted and even grown more extractive. The research calls for deep-rooted structural and cultural reforms that address both the legal and human dimensions of policing in Pakistan. The judicial practices and trial procedures in Pakistan remain deeply influenced by colonial procedural formalism. The adversarial system, inherited from British common law, often functions in a manner that prioritizes technicality over substantive justice.

For the first time in Pakistan's history in June, 2021, the then government introduced nearly 700 proposed amendments to overhaul the colonial-era criminal justice system. Spearheaded by the Ministry of Law and Justice, the amendments span key statutes including the Code of Criminal Procedure 1898 (CrPC), Pakistan Penal Code 1860 (PPC), and Qanoon-e-Shahadat Order, 1984 (QSO), aiming to enhance efficiency, ensure timely justice, and protect vulnerable segments of society such as women, children, and the mentally ill. The federal government emphasized the accessibility of justice and reduction of judicial backlog, with specific reforms mandating nine-month deadlines for criminal trials and limiting adjournments to three days, except in exceptional cases. (Iqbal, 2022)

According to data obtained from the Law and Justice Commission of Pakistan, as of December 31st, 2024, **2.362 million cases** are pending in all courts across the country, of which 83 percent (1.955 million) are pending in the country's district courts, 17 percent (0.4637 million) cases are pending in the high courts, whereas according to data from the Supreme Court's website, 57,089 cases were pending as of August 6th 2025, even after the appointment of eight new judges in the last six months. Currently, the court is not functioning at full strength due to the summer vacation, contributing to the increase in pending cases. Just last week, 56,892 cases were recorded as pending.

Amendments to Criminal Procedure Code (CrPC) section 250 discourage frivolous litigation by significantly increasing penalties for false accusations. Recognizing technological advancement, revisions to Article 164 of the Qanoon-e-Shahadat Order, 1984 (QSO) now permit evidence gathered through modern devices, including audio and video

recordings. Additionally, it was proposed a new chapter introduces plea bargains to expedite trials excluding crimes involving women, children, or those affecting socio-economic stability. Further safeguarding women, new provisions criminalize stalking and amend arrest protocols to prevent manhandling by male officers. Rules regarding the arrest and trial of women, minors, elderly, and the disabled have also been updated to reflect sensitivity and protection.

The Supreme Court of Pakistan's landmark judgment in *Safia Bano vs Home Department, Government of Punjab* (PLD 2021 SC 488) marked a transformative shift in the treatment of mentally ill prisoners, banning executions where a recognized mental disorder substantially impairs a condemned person's ability to comprehend the nature or rationale of their punishment. The consolidated cases of Imdad Ali, Kaneezan Bibi, and Ghulam Abbas each involving long-term incarceration and documented mental illness prompted the Court to direct the establishment of medical boards in all provinces to assess prisoners' mental health, modernize outdated legal definitions, and replace derogatory terms such as "lunatic" with clinically accurate language aligned with WHO standards.

Drawing on comparative jurisprudence from the UK, India, and the US, as well as international human rights conventions, the Court held that executing the mentally ill fails to serve retributive or deterrent goals and undermines rehabilitative justice principles. It distinguished between mental capacity at the time of offence (Section 84 PPC) and competence to stand trial (Sections 464-465 CrPC), emphasizing that judicial opinion must be supported by professional psychiatric evidence. The Court reduced the death sentences of Ali and Bibi to life imprisonment, citing factors such as prolonged imprisonment and legitimate expectancy of life, while maintaining their convictions. The ruling overruled earlier precedent that excluded schizophrenia from the ambit of permanent mental disorders, affirming it as a basis for commutation. Analytically, the decision is grounded in two principles: that executing mentally ill prisoners is ineffective and unfair, and that it violates the constitutional right to a fair trial by punishing individuals unable to fully understand their actions or legal proceedings. Nonetheless, the

judgment exposes systemic gaps, notably the burden placed on defendants to prove mental illness despite widespread lack of psychiatric care and legal resources, risking uneven application of justice. While heralded as progressive and protective of a marginalized group, the case underscores the need for structural reforms to ensure its rehabilitative promise is realized in Pakistan's criminal justice system, therefore, in light of the *Safia Bano* case, reforms now mandate psychological evaluations by medical boards before executing mentally ill prisoners, replacing outdated terminology and ensuring humane treatment. (Ranjha & Fatima, n.d.) Prison rules were also revised to protect the dignity of female convicts during executions. To deter absconders, courts may now block Citizens National Identification Cards (CNICs) and travel documents of proclaimed offenders. Notably, the death penalty under Section 9(c) of the Control of Narcotics Substances Act, 1997 has been replaced with life imprisonment, aligning with international human rights norms. While these reforms signify a major step forward modernizing Pakistan's criminal justice system with a rights-based approach, the Supreme Court Bar Association has criticized the lack of consultation with legal stakeholders. Nevertheless, the urgency and comprehensiveness of these reforms underscore their necessity in addressing the system's long-standing structural deficiencies. (Iqbal, 2022)

Pakistan's prison system is a colonial legacy inherited from British India post-1947, initially used to detain political opponents and criminals. Over time, deteriorating prison conditions and rising concerns from governments and human rights organizations have underscored the urgent need for reform, especially as prison environments correlate directly with recidivism and criminal behavior. Global shifts in penal philosophy from retribution to rehabilitation have prompted several commissions in Pakistan to recommend structural reforms focusing on custody, care, control, correction, cure, and community reintegration. Despite these recommendations, implementation has lagged significantly due to financial constraints, administrative inefficiencies, outdated laws, and provincial-level neglect. The prison infrastructure, largely from the 19th century, is overcrowded, underfunded, and unable to meet international

standards of prisoner care. Prisons in Pakistan remain plagued by corruption, coercion, custodial abuse, class-based discrimination, poor healthcare, and the absence of effective rehabilitation programs. The juvenile justice system has seen modest improvement since the implementation of the Juvenile Justice System Ordinance, 2000 (JJSO 2000), reducing the number of incarcerated children. However, facilities for women and young offenders remain inadequate. A comprehensive review of legislation, particularly the Prison Rules and parole/probation frameworks, is necessary. Equally important is the training and capacity-building of prison staff, establishment of provincial-level reform institutions, and integration of international human rights instruments. Reform efforts must consider the interdependence of prisons with the broader criminal justice system, emphasizing community-based rehabilitation and ensuring the dignity and rights of all prisoners. Without robust provincial commitment and multilayered reformation strategies, prisons will continue to serve as breeding grounds for criminal behavior rather than centers of correction and rehabilitation. (Akbar & Bhutta, n.d.)

Pakistan's legal framework regarding punishment is not an entirely indigenous development; it is deeply rooted in the British colonial legal system inherited at the time of independence. Despite this inherited structure, Pakistan's unique religious, cultural, and social context gradually reshaped the system to reflect its Islamic identity. This legal evolution reflects a complex fusion of colonial heritage and Islamic revivalism, shaping the nature of punishment in the country. Muhammad Ali Jinnah, Pakistan's founding leader, envisioned a state that upheld Islamic values not only culturally but also within its legal and judicial systems. Although trained in British legal traditions, Jinnah emphasized the importance of constructing a legal framework grounded in Islamic principles as a complete social and moral system. However, due to the urgency and lack of political space at the time of independence, Pakistan continued with the colonial legal setup, including laws such as the Pakistan Penal Code, 1860 (PPC) formerly the Indian Penal Code which remained in force despite its Western jurisprudential roots. Over time, however, a gradual shift began toward the incorporation of Shariah principles. Religious

scholars, lawmakers, and societal leaders raised concerns about legal provisions inconsistent with Islamic teachings. The aim was not to dismantle the legal order but to align it with the religious and moral values foundational to the state's identity. Amendments began to reflect Islamic perspectives, such as the prohibition of alcohol, the criminalization of *zina* (fornication and adultery), and the reinforcement of public morality laws. These reforms illustrated a transition from maintaining colonial order to upholding religious ethics. The most significant transformation occurred during General Zia-ul-Haq's regime in the late 1970s, with the introduction of the Hudood Ordinances. These laws were enacted to bring the criminal justice system closer to the Qur'an and Sunnah, introducing fixed Islamic punishments (*hudoood*) for offenses such as theft, adultery, false accusation (*Qazf*), and alcohol consumption. While this ordinance operated alongside the Pakistan Penal Code (PPC), they marked a bold step toward legal Islamization. (Zulfiqar, 2025)

Furthermore, in 2022 the law ministry's amendments Code of Criminal Procedure, 1998 (CrPC), the Qanoon-e-Shahadat (law of evidence), Pakistan Penal Code 1860 (PPC) and other relevant laws approved by the federal cabinet by envision a nine-month deadline for the completion of criminal trials; the introduction of plea-bargains and the use of modern tools and technology in the investigation process. (Asad. 2022)

This research presents a critical analysis of the structural inefficiencies and procedural obstacles within Pakistan's criminal justice system, specifically focusing on the Balochistan province. Through a blend of qualitative interviews, survey data, and document analysis, the study reveals systemic deficiencies in areas such as policing, prosecution, judiciary, prison management, parole, and probation. Additionally, it references international models, including the inquisitorial systems of France and Germany, to pinpoint best practices that could be adapted to the Pakistani context. The research also suggests a comprehensive reform strategy involving multiple stakeholders, aimed at legislative modernization, improved institutional coordination, capacity enhancement, and the integration of technology. The study concludes by underscoring the

importance of civic education and the underutilized potential of educators in enhancing public legal awareness. This combined legal and educational strategy is crucial for establishing a transparent, efficient, and accountable justice system in Pakistan. (Uddin & Bibi, 2025)

This study considers the convergences between colonial “lawfare”, (post) colonial counterinsurgency, and domestic policing to explore how such convergences facilitate the criminalization and punishment of dissent and activism within contemporary undemocratic or authoritarian contexts. Using colonial-era legislations found in Pakistan, I explore how such frameworks are deployed as part of a postcolonial state’s overarching counterinsurgency warfare against citizens and employ postcolonial perspectives to show how such colonial institutions legitimize and weaponize the state’s militarized lawfare against its people and frame socio-political activism and critical resistance as conspiracies amounting to national security threats, revealing continuities between colonial and postcolonial policing of resistance. Such securitized narrative-framing, coupled with the deployment of colonial-era techniques of control, further ensures an ongoing conflation of “police power” and “war power”. (Zoha Waseem, 2024)

The then Prime Minister announced comprehensive criminal justice reforms aimed at ensuring equal justice for both the rich and the poor, emphasizing the government’s commitment to the rule of law and faster dispensation of justice. The reforms, described as historic, involve over 700 amendments to key laws including the Criminal Procedure Code (1898), Pakistan Penal Code (1860), and Qanun-e-Shahadat (1984), effectively overhauling Pakistan’s legal system. Law Minister highlighted major changes such as the establishment of an independent prosecution service, forensic labs, prison rules, and a mandatory budget for police investigations. Measures include ensuring trials are completed within nine months, appeals in six, and holding judges accountable for delays. Key reforms also involve electronic first information report (FIR) registration, audio/video recording of witness statements and testimonies, and blocking official identification cards (IDs) and bank accounts of absconders. New mechanisms have been introduced for plea bargaining excluding serious

crimes and the use of modern technology for evidence submission. The reforms also aim to prevent misuse of legal processes, such as penalizing false cases and introducing stricter punishments, including for crimes like stalking women. Civil reforms stress accountability and coordination between police, prosecutors, and judiciary. Furthermore, proposals include safeguarding the rights of arrestees, especially women, and regulating arms in public gatherings. Overall, these changes represent a significant step towards an efficient, transparent, and equitable criminal justice system in Pakistan. (International the Newes, 2022)

Pakistan’s criminal justice system has long been fraught with challenges including mal-administration, corruption, abuse of power, lack of resources, and systemic rigidity, all of which hinder the delivery of prompt and equitable justice. Despite numerous legislative and judicial reforms, the system continues to fail victims and the accused alike due to delays in case resolution, police brutality, inadequate legal aid, lack of witness protection, and widespread corruption within law enforcement institutions and the judiciary. Other pressing concerns include political interference, outdated colonial-era laws, poor infrastructure, ineffective monitoring, and insufficient training for legal personnel. The article stresses the urgent need for reforms through anti-corruption measures, technological integration, the establishment of performance indicators, modernization of investigation techniques, judicial empowerment, and expansion of legal aid services. Suggestions include developing independent oversight bodies, enhancing transparency through information Technology solutions, strengthening the parole and probation system, implementing restorative justice practices, and drawing lessons from reforms in the United States. and South Africa such as body cams (body cameras), bail reform, and independent police oversight. Ultimately, comprehensive collaboration, political will, and strategic policymaking are essential to transform Pakistan’s dysfunctional justice system into a more fair, efficient, and accountable institution. (Rafique, 2023)

The recommendation of Rehman, Usmani, and Parveen (2021) that Police registration of first information reports (FIRs) and related legislation

should not justify arrests; arrests must be based on court-issued warrants after evaluating police evidence. Maintaining digital first information report (FIR) records at police stations is essential. Citizens should be able to track first information report (FIR) progress and report negligence. Online computerization of first information report (FIRs), investigations, court procedures, and coordination with prison authorities will enhance transparency and reduce delays. (Rehman, Usmani, & Parveen, 2021)

The Pakistan Law Commission identified critical issues within the Code of Criminal Procedure, 1898, prompting a set of proposed amendments in 1993 to address outdated provisions and systemic inefficiencies. Public complaints revealed that certain provisions allowed abuse of power by police officials, caused undue hardship to accused persons and their families, and failed to effectively deter perjury. Key concerns included police not informing family members of arrests under Sections 54 and 55; refusal to register first information reports (FIRs) under section 154; non-compliance with Section 167(4) regarding the Magistrate giving such, order shall forward a copy of his order, with his reasons for making it, to Sessions Judges about detention orders; lack of punishment for perjury under section 382-A; termination of appeals upon the death of the convict appellant under section 431; and procedural hurdles in prosecuting false evidence under Section 476-A. To rectify these issues, the Commission proposed substantial amendments. These included inserting section 59A, which mandated that arrested persons be entitled to have a relative or friend informed, with limited exceptions permitted only by a senior police officer on specific grounds. It also recommended allowing complainants to register first information report (FIRs) directly with a Magistrate under a new sub-section (2) of section 154, with corresponding amendments in section 156. Furthermore, section 167(4) was to be strengthened by requiring that Magistrates immediately inform Sessions Judges upon authorizing detention.

A major reform proposed was to amend section 431 and add section 431-A, ensuring the right to appeal would not abate upon the convict's death if requested by legal heirs, even before filing the appeal. To combat perjury, the Commission recommended

repealing section 476-A and substituting a new section 476, empowering courts to take cognizance of false evidence or fabricated reports by police officers or experts during trials, and to conduct summary trials without referring such matters to other courts. Clause (a) of section 382-A was also proposed for removal to eliminate delays in perjury proceedings.

Although the Commission submitted these amendments through the Code of Criminal Procedure (Amendment) Bill, 1993, the recommendations were largely unadopted, except for limited explanations added to sections 58 and 82 concerning their applicability to Azad Jammu and Kashmir. The overarching objective of these reforms was to safeguard fundamental rights, improve transparency and accountability within the criminal justice system, and empower courts to more effectively curb procedural abuses and injustices. (Law and Justice Commission of Pakistan, 1993)

In sum, the literature converges on the argument that Pakistan's criminal justice crisis is not merely a function of contemporary failures but is structurally rooted in its colonial inheritance. Any attempt at reform must begin by acknowledging this historical burden and engaging in a holistic, culturally resonant, and democratically anchored transformation of the system. The challenge is not only legal or institutional but fundamentally ideological requiring a shift from control to service, from coercion to justice.

METHODOLOGY:

The research paper adopts a qualitative methodology rooted in doctrinal legal analysis, comparative institutional review, and empirical inquiry through semi-structured interviews. The chosen methodology reflects the nature and complexity of the subject matter, which encompasses both historical-legal evolution and contemporary institutional challenges within Pakistan's criminal justice system. A qualitative approach enables an in-depth, contextual, and interpretive understanding of how colonial-era legacies have shaped, and continue to influence, present-day legal institutions, procedures, and enforcement mechanisms.

1. Research Design: The study utilizes a multi-method qualitative research design, combining the following approaches:

- **Doctrinal Legal Research:** This traditional method of legal inquiry involves a critical analysis of primary legal materials such as statutes, case laws, constitutional provisions, and colonial-era legal instruments. It is used to trace the historical continuity of key legal frameworks especially the Criminal Procedure Code 1898 (CRPc), the Police Act 1861, and the Pakistan Penal Code 1860 (PPC) to assess how they have evolved (or failed to evolve) since independence.
- **Empirical Research through Semi-Structured Interviews:** To supplement the doctrinal legal research, a series of semi-structured interviews were conducted with key stakeholders, including:
 - Legal practitioners (judges, lawyers)
 - Police officers (both serving and retired)
 - Human rights activists
 - Academics and researchers specializing in criminal law and post-colonial governance

These interviews aimed to capture practical insights and lived experiences regarding procedural inefficiencies, accountability deficits, and reform priorities.

2. Data Collection: The study collected data by primary and secondary sources for in-depth analysis, by adopting the following ways.

a. Primary Sources:

- **Legal Texts:** Statutes including the Code of Criminal Procedure 1898 (CRPc), Pakistan Penal Code 1860 (PPC), Police Act 1861, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa Provincial Police Laws i.e., Police Order 2002, Police Act 2017, and Police Amendment Act 2024, furthermore, the relevant constitutional provisions for criminal justice system were also considered.

- **Official Policy Documents:** National and provincial criminal justice reform plans, police training manuals, and parliamentary committee reports on justice sector performance.
- **Interview Transcripts:** Approximately 15-20 interviews were conducted in English and Urdu, with informed consent, ensuring the anonymity of respondents.

b. Secondary Sources:

- **Scholarly Articles:** Peer-reviewed journal articles and legal commentaries on colonial law, justice reforms, and comparative criminal justice systems.
- **Books and Reports:** Publications by NGOs, UN agencies, and local legal research bodies (e.g., International Crisis Group, Human Rights Commission of Pakistan, LEAD Pakistan).
- **Media and Press Releases:** Reports on recent legal reforms, political interference in the judiciary, and public response to high-profile criminal cases.

3. Data Analysis: The collected data were analyzed using thematic content analysis, where textual materials and interview transcripts were coded and categorized according to recurring themes such as:

- Colonial influence on legal procedures and police behavior,
- Political manipulation and bureaucratic resistance,
- Gaps in legal aid, access to justice, and public trust,
- Institutional reform priorities and stakeholder perspectives.

Patterns of continuity and transformation were identified by triangulating legal documents with stakeholder interviews and comparative benchmarks.

4. Ethical Considerations: This study adhered to ethical standards applicable to legal and social research. Participants were informed about the

objectives of the research and provided written or verbal consent before interviews. Confidentiality and anonymity were maintained throughout, particularly where respondents shared critical views about institutions or officials. No financial incentives were provided, and participation was entirely voluntary.

5. Limitations of the Study: While the study provides a robust qualitative analysis, certain limitations are acknowledged:

- The sample size for interviews, while sufficient for thematic saturation, may not fully represent all institutional actors.
- The historical-doctrinal approach may face constraints in directly assessing lived experiences of justice seekers at the grassroots level.
- The study does not include a comprehensive statistical or quantitative analysis due to the focus on legal structure, perception, and institutional behavior rather than numerical trends.

Despite these limitations, the research offers a nuanced and contextually grounded understanding of the structural impediments to criminal justice reform in Pakistan and proposes actionable reforms based on legal precedent, comparative insights, and stakeholder input.

RESULTS AND ANALYSIS:

A critical analysis of primary legal documents, including the Criminal Procedure Code of 1898, the Pakistan Penal Code of 1860, the Police Act of 1861, revealed minimal substantive evolution since their colonial inception. Despite legislative updates such as the Khyber Pakhtunkhwa Police Order 2002, Police Act 2017 & recent amendment of 2024 in Police Act, 2017 etc. Various interviews with police officials and legal professionals indicated that the operational ethos remains rooted in control-oriented top to down governance. Police practices are still dominated by coercive techniques, unchecked discretion, and an emphasis on maintaining "order" rather than upholding rights and justice.

Interview Insight:

A retired superintendent of police observed, "Our training and hierarchy are still based on the logic of

colonial command not community service. Accountability exists more in theory than in practice."

The doctrinal review and judicial case analysis highlighted significant procedural inefficiencies embedded within the judicial process. Interview data reinforced that courts remain overburdened with excessive caseloads, largely due to outdated procedural rules and formalistic trial practices that delay justice delivery.

Key findings include:

- **Pre-trial detentions** often last years due to procedural delays and slow police investigations.
- **Adversarial trial mechanisms**, inherited from British common law, favor procedural technicalities over substantive justice, disproportionately disadvantaging the poor and unrepresented.
- **Witness protection** remains virtually nonexistent, compromising the reliability of testimonies and case outcomes.

Analysis of prison reports and legal judgments confirmed that Pakistan's penal philosophy is largely retributive. Prisons remain overcrowded and under-resourced, lacking rehabilitative programming or alternatives to incarceration. Under-trial prisoners constitute over 60% of the incarcerated population, often imprisoned for petty offenses.

Interview Insight:

A human rights advocate noted, "Our prisons are colonial relics they are still used to punish the poor and powerless, not rehabilitate or reform."

The research identified a complex interaction between colonial legacies and present-day challenges:

- **Political interference** in policing and prosecution undermines institutional independence.

- **Lack of coordination** between justice sector actors leads to reform fatigue and implementation failure.
- **Bureaucratic inertia** resists systemic transformation, favoring cosmetic over structural changes.

Interview Insight:

A district court judge commented, "Even when reforms are proposed, they rarely make it past the bureaucratic machinery there's too much vested interest in the status quo."

Legal aid remains underfunded and inconsistently available. Most poor defendants face trials without competent legal representation. This contributes to a widening gap between law and justice, particularly for marginalized communities.

Public Trust: Survey responses and interviews reflected a general distrust in the justice system, perceived as slow, biased, and inaccessible. People often rely on informal justice mechanisms (e.g., jirgas, panchayats) out of frustration or fear of formal institutions.

Empirical Observation: Legal aid lawyers interviewed emphasized that even when aid is available, institutional delays and limited resources hamper effective representation.

Comparative institutional analysis revealed more robust reform trajectories in countries like South Africa and Bangladesh:

- **South Africa** has incorporated community policing and restorative justice principles with moderate success.
- **Bangladesh**, while also struggling with colonial legacies, has advanced digital court systems and established specialized tribunals to expedite justice in key areas.

These models demonstrate that post-colonial reform is possible when guided by political will, community engagement, and a reimagining of justice values. Thematic analysis of interviews highlighted consensus on several reform priorities:

- **Modernization of Policing:** Independent police commissions, community oversight, and training on human rights.
- **Judicial Reform:** Procedural simplification, digitization of court systems, and enhanced judicial training.
- **Legal Education Reform:** Reorienting legal curricula to emphasize constitutional rights, restorative justice, and critical post-colonial legal analysis.
- **Restorative Justice Promotion:** Especially for non-violent and juvenile offenses, to reduce prison populations and reintegrate offenders.

Pakistan is ranked 130 out of 139 nations analyzed by the World Justice Project regarding "adherence to the rule of law" indexed 2021 report. Regrettably, Afghanistan was the only country in the area to rank worse than Pakistan. Similarly, Pakistan's criminal justice and civil justice systems were placed fourth among the region's six reviewed nations (Abbasi, 2021; Ahmad, 2021). Even the then Prime Minister admitted that criminal justice system (CJS) reforms in Pakistan are his top priority (Raza, 2021). Pakistan's inefficient CJS has grave implications for internal, regional, and international security (Dawn, 2021).

The findings confirm that Pakistan's criminal justice system is structurally compromised by a dual burden: the inertia of colonial legacies and the weight of contemporary dysfunction. These forces converge to sustain a justice system that is slow, inequitable, and repressive rather than rights-based or service-oriented.

Without a conscious process of legal and institutional decolonization supported by legislative action, capacity building, and inclusive reform planning Pakistan risks perpetuating cycles of injustice.

DISCUSSIONS & RECOMANDATIONS:

The findings of this research reveal a sobering reality: Pakistan's criminal justice system is deeply entrenched in colonial legacies, both structurally and

ideologically. Despite legislative amendments and judicial decisions over the decades, meaningful reforms in policing, prosecution, and the judiciary remain elusive. These sectors continue to operate within frameworks originally designed to control and suppress, rather than to protect, serve, and deliver justice. The institutional inertia that resists reform is reinforced by contemporary dysfunctions: political interference, bureaucratic inefficiency, lack of accountability, and resource constraints which converge to maintain a system that is unresponsive to the needs of a democratic, rights-based society.

Reforming the Police Sector: The police system in Pakistan continues to reflect the colonial Royal Irish Constabulary model, where the primary aim was to maintain order and suppress dissent. This legacy endures in the form of top to down command structures, coercive tactics, and unchecked discretion. As observed during interviews, police training, ethos, and operational style are still focused more on authority than service. To reform this colonial legacy, the following measures are recommended:

1. Decolonize Policing Culture: Shift the orientation of police training from coercion and obedience to public service, community engagement, and human rights education.

2. Establishment and Activation of Independent Police Oversight Commissions: A significant reform highlighted in the literature is the establishment of independent police oversight bodies namely, the Khyber Pakhtunkhwa Public Safety Commissions, created under the Police Order 2002 at the provincial, capital city district, and district levels of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa.

These oversight mechanisms were further strengthened by the Khyber Pakhtunkhwa Police Act 2017 and the Police Amendment Act 2024. Notably, recent legislative amendments of 2024 under sections 48 to 65 have broadened the composition of these commissions to include representatives from provincial/national assemblies, civil society, legal experts (retired judges & advocates), and retired bureaucrats, aiming to enhance transparency and reinforce police accountability.

Furthermore, Regional Police Complaint Authorities at Regional level under section 66 to 72 of Police Amendment Act 2024 were also established for enquiring into complaints of police excesses, other than relating to investigations, against all Police officials up-to the rank of Assistant Superintendent of Police or Deputy.

However, despite this robust legal framework, these commissions and authorities remain largely dormant in practice. Their role has been reduced to a symbolic presence rather than an active force for reform. They are often under resourced, lack operational autonomy, and fail to fulfill their intended oversight functions effectively. To address this gap, it is imperative to fully activate and institutionalize these commissions and authorities, not just on paper but in actual practice. These bodies must be empowered with the necessary power, resources, and independence to carry out their mandate without political or bureaucratic interference. Moreover, similar independent police oversight institutions should be established and operationalized across all provinces and territories of Pakistan to ensure a uniform, accountable, and transparent policing system nationwide.

3. Modernize Investigation Techniques: Invest in forensic labs, data systems, and digital evidence tools. The use of technology (e.g., body cameras, automated FIR systems) will reduce corruption and enhance efficiency.

4. Ensure Institutional Autonomy: Free the police from political manipulation by guaranteeing tenure protections, promoting merit-based appointments, and separating investigation from prosecution roles.

5. Implement Community Policing Models: Inspired by successful initiatives in South Africa and the UK, such models build trust and cooperation between police and the communities they serve.

Reforming the Prosecution System: The prosecutorial system remains underdeveloped, underfunded, and dependent on defective police investigations. Coordination between police and prosecutors is often weak, with charge sheets and

evidence presented in court lacking legal sufficiency, which undermines the integrity of criminal trials.

Recommendations for prosecutorial reform include:

1. Empower Prosecutors in Early Investigation Stages: Amend laws to involve prosecutors from the outset of investigations, especially in scrutinizing first information reports (FIRs) and evidence collection.

2. Strengthen Training and Resources: Establish continuous professional development programs on evidence evaluation, digital forensics, and rights-based prosecution.

3. Ensure Prosecutorial Independence: Create a constitutionally protected, independent prosecution service that is free from executive and political pressure.

4. Reform Section 173 CrPC: Streamline the process of submitting investigation reports, ensuring timelines and allowing prosecutors real authority to reject deficient reports.

Judicial Reforms: The judicial system, heavily influenced by British formalism, continues to favor procedural rigidity over substantive justice. Trials are often prolonged due to outdated rules, backlog of cases, and adversarial court procedures that disadvantage the poor and unrepresented. The research also highlighted the problematic use of pre-trial detention, the lack of witness protection, and the absence of digitized processes.

Key judicial reforms include:

1. Procedural Simplification: Revise the Criminal Procedure Code (CrPC) and Qanun-e-Shahadat to streamline trials, reduce adjournments, and encourage evidence-based judgments rather than procedural technicalities.

2. Digitization of Court Processes: Introduce and strengthen automated case management systems, online hearings, and electronic evidence submissions to reduce delay and human discretion.

3. Accountability Mechanisms for Judges: Establish performance indicators and independent judicial oversight to assess case disposal rates and professional conduct.

4. Legal Aid Expansion: Allocate funds and develop infrastructure for effective legal aid services, particularly for the indigent and marginalized.

5. Witness Protection Program: Develop a national policy for witness safety to enhance the credibility of testimonies and ensure fair trials.

6. Promotion of Restorative Justice: Encourage alternatives to incarceration such as community service, mediation, and victim-offender reconciliation for non-violent crimes, particularly for juveniles and first-time offenders.

Legislative and Structural Reforms: Reform must be legislative and structural, not just administrative. Outdated laws like the PPC 1860, CrPC 1898 and Police Act 1861 require comprehensive overhaul. The amendments proposed by the Law and Justice Commission of Pakistan and the recent 700-plus amendments proposed by the federal government offer a good starting point, but they must be followed by structured implementation plans.

1. Adopt Time-Bound Trial Frameworks: Enforce deadlines (e.g., nine months for trial completion) with consequences for non-compliance to prevent indefinite delays.

2. Revise Outdated Penal Provisions: Remove colonial-era offenses that no longer reflect the socio-political realities or human rights standards of a modern state.

3. Introduce Plea Bargaining with Safeguards: Plea bargaining mechanisms can reduce backlog but must be restricted in cases involving gender-based violence, minors, or socio-economic exploitation.

4. Promote Judicial Activism in Legislative Reform: Encourage the judiciary to proactively identify and recommend legislative gaps through constitutional interpretation and Suo- Motu action

under article 184(3) whereas Suo-Motu action now only be initiated/taken on the application of the party after 26th amendment.

Prison and Punishment Reforms: The penal philosophy of Pakistan remains rooted in retribution, not rehabilitation. Prisons continue to be overcrowded, underfunded, and violent spaces, failing to offer meaningful correction or reintegration.

Recommendations include:

1. Reform Prison Infrastructure and Management: Modernize facilities, ensure health and mental care, and eliminate class-based discrimination in incarceration.

2. Develop Rehabilitation Programs: Introduce vocational training, education, and counseling to facilitate post-incarceration reintegration.

3. Update Prison Rules in Light of Human Rights Norms: Implement Safia Bano case guidelines for mentally ill prisoners and ensure gender-sensitive execution protocols.

4. Expand Non-Custodial Sentences: Encourage probation, parole, and community-based corrections, particularly for minor and non-violent offenders.

Recommendations for Cross-Sectoral Reform

1. Establish Coordinated Justice Sector Councils: Facilitate cooperation between police, prosecutors, courts, and prisons to eliminate procedural bottlenecks and jurisdictional confusion.

2. Civic Legal Education and Awareness: Promote legal literacy through media, school curricula, and bar associations to empower citizens with their rights and responsibilities.

3. Institutionalize Research and Policy Think-Tanks: Set up criminal justice reform units within law schools and the Ministry of Law to conduct ongoing assessments and develop reform agendas.

4. Strengthen Inter-Provincial and Federal Coordination: Uniform reform policies across provinces are necessary to avoid fragmentation and duplication of effort.

Pakistan's criminal justice system is not merely a legal structure in need of reform; it is an institution burdened by its colonial history and paralyzed by modern dysfunction. Genuine transformation must begin with the decolonization of legal consciousness, supported by legislative overhaul, institutional restructuring, civic engagement, and resource investment. Reform must be comprehensive, inclusive, and sustained not symbolic or reactionary. By embracing a rights-based, service-oriented approach to justice, Pakistan can move beyond its colonial past and towards a future where the law serves all citizens equitably and with dignity. Only then can the country realize the constitutional promise of justice, liberty, and equality for all.

CONCLUSION:

This research concludes that Pakistan's criminal justice system remains profoundly shaped by colonial legacies, manifesting in authoritarian policing practices, rigid judicial procedures, and an underdeveloped prosecution mechanism. Despite numerous reforms on paper, the reality on the ground remains one of systemic dysfunction, where justice is often delayed, denied, or distorted. The persistence of outdated laws, coupled with political interference, bureaucratic inefficiency, and a lack of accountability, has sustained a structure designed more for control than for service and protection in a democratic society.

Reforming such a deeply embedded system demands more than administrative tweaks; it requires a paradigm shift. The findings of this study emphasize the urgent need to decolonize the ethos and operations of policing by transforming it into a service-oriented, rights-based institution.

Prosecutorial independence, professional capacity-building, and early-stage involvement in investigations must be ensured to bolster fair and efficient criminal trials. Similarly, the judiciary must move away from procedural rigidity toward expeditious, technology-enabled, and victim-centered justice. Procedural simplification, digitization,

judicial accountability, and expansion of legal aid services can no longer be delayed if access to justice is to be made a reality for all, especially the marginalized.

Equally important are the legislative and structural reforms needed to replace the antiquated Code of Criminal Procedure and Police Act with frameworks suited to Pakistan's contemporary needs. Penal reforms must shift the philosophy of punishment from retribution to rehabilitation, ensuring that prisons become spaces of reform rather than perpetrators of social exclusion. Non-custodial sentences, rehabilitation programs, and updated prison management systems must be institutionalized. Reform must also be systemic and interconnected. Coordinated justice sector councils, legal education campaigns, and independent research institutions are essential to foster a culture of evidence-based policy-making and continuous institutional evolution. Uniformity in implementation across provinces through federal-provincial coordination will be key to preventing fragmentation and duplication.

Ultimately, Pakistan's path to justice reform is not just a legal or institutional challenge it is a moral and constitutional imperative. Only by shedding the vestiges of colonialism and reimagining the criminal justice system as a guardian of rights, dignity, and fairness can Pakistan fulfill its constitutional promise. Reform must be comprehensive, sustained, and rooted in a vision of justice that values humanity over hierarchy, rights over repression, and service over subjugation. Only then can the law truly become a shield for the vulnerable and a beacon of hope for the nation.

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